

INTEGRATED FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF SMART COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: With the increasing use of smart materials and smart structural systems for space and other structural applications, there is an increasing need for advanced analysis and design tools for this class of structures. The study presented herein was undertaken to develop a computational tool which is suitable for the design/analysis of smart materials and structures with integrated control capabilities. In this paper an integrated finite element-control modelling capability for composite structures with piezoelectric sensors and actuators is presented. The method is based on a 20-node thermopiezoelectric finite element and the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) and independent modal space control (IMSC) algorithms. A design/analysis software, called SMARTCOM, has been developed based on the methodology. The efficacy of the method is demonstrated by analyzing several active and sensory structural systems with control capabilities. The results show that SMARTCOM can be efficiently used for the analysis and design of composite structures with piezoelectric sensors and actuators, with various loading conditions and control requirements.

KEYWORDS: thermopiezoelectricity, LQR, IMSC, vibration control, smart materials and structures, SMARTCOM

INTRODUCTION

Smart materials and smart structural systems are increasingly attracting attention from the research community because of their importance in current and future high performance structural applications. Examples of high performance structures requiring smart material and smart structures concepts include space antennas, precision optical systems and large solar arrays. The concepts have commonly been demonstrated for vibration and shape control of structural components such as beams and plates. These active structures have their own sensors, actuators and control capabilities in an integrated fashion. Piezoelectric materials have shown promise as sensor and actuators for many applications and control has been achieved by several methods, such as the independent modal space control (IMSC) and the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) methods [1,2].

In order to design or analyze smart structures for existing or new structural systems, it is essential to understand the behaviour of the integrated structure comprising of the structure, sensors, actuators and the control method. Because of the complex behaviour of these structural systems, the finite element method is considered to be an effective method for analyzing them. Some studies on finite element modelling of composite structures with piezoelectric sensors and actuators with control capabilities have been carried out in recent years [1,3-8]. However, in spite of these efforts there is still an increasing need for advanced analysis and design tools for this class of structures because most of the currently available

tools are based on specialized programs which are not suitable for many realistic problems, and are also not widely available. This study was undertaken to develop a computerized tool, within the framework of a general purpose finite element analysis software, which is suitable for the design/analysis of various types of smart materials/structures and control capabilities. The overall objectives of the study also include fuzzy and probabilistic based optimization and reliability assessment of the structure-integrated control systems.

In this paper an integrated finite element modelling capability for composite structures with surface bonded piezoceramic sensors and actuators is presented. The method, which is completely general, is based on a 20 node thermopiezoelectric finite element and control algorithms based on the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) and the independent modal space control (IMSC). The finite element solution strategy is derived from the general purpose finite element program called VAST [9] and the method has been implemented in the overall smart structures design/analysis software called SMARTCOM [10]. The theoretical foundations on which the method is based are described and some applications of the computational tool for the analysis/design of structures for vibration control are presented.

THEORETICAL FORMULATIONS

Finite Element Model

As stated above, the finite element method is used to model the smart structure comprising the structure, sensors and actuators. Each of these structural components of the smart structure is modelled by a twenty node layered composite brick element with thermopiezoelectric properties. The choice of this element was based on the fact that being a quadratic element it is more accurate than the eight noded brick element frequently used to model piezoelectric materials. In addition it does not require the use of incompatible displacement modes to improve bending response as does the eight noded brick, and it would require fewer elements to model the structure. The fact that fewer elements can be used to provide reasonably accurate results makes it suitable for design. However, it should be pointed out that this element is more computation intensive than the eight node solid element.

The most general formulation of the element, with mechanical, thermal and electrical effects considered, was developed and implemented in SMARTCOM. The element was developed as a layered composite element with orthotropic material properties. As SMARTCOM is expected to be a stand alone finite element design package, the formulation of the element was done so that problems with only mechanical, thermal, electrical, or any possible combinations of these effects with or without control can be analyzed. In the following subsections, a brief description of the thermopiezoelectric finite element formulation is provided. Details can be found in [5,6,11].

Finite Element Discretization and Shape Functions

The element has 20 nodes and the node numbering and shape functions are the same as the standard twenty noded brick element. The effects of the mechanical, electrical and thermal

(u, ϕ, θ , respectively) variables are included, such that there are five degrees-of-freedom at each element node. The element extended displacement field is given by $\bar{u}_i = \sum_{j=1}^{20} \delta_{ij} N_j$ where $\delta_{ij}^T = [u_1, u_2, u_3, \phi, \theta]$ are the displacements for $i=1,2,\dots,5$ at the nodal points $j=1,2,\dots,20$. N_j are the element shape functions which can be found in any standard text (eg Ref. 12).

Strain-Displacement Relations

The relationships between the extended strains $\bar{\epsilon}_s$ and the extended displacements are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon}_s^T &= [\epsilon_{11} \ \epsilon_{22} \ \epsilon_{33} \ 2\epsilon_{12} \ 2\epsilon_{23} \ 2\epsilon_{31} \ -E_1 \ -E_2 \ -E_3 \ -g_1 \ -g_2 \ -g_3] \\ &= [B_u \{\delta^u\}, B_\phi \{\delta^\phi\}, B_\theta \{\delta^\theta\}] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $B_u = [\mathcal{L}_u] \{\delta^u\}$, $B_\phi = [\mathcal{L}_\phi] \{\delta^\phi\}$ and $B_\theta = [\mathcal{L}_\theta] \{\delta^\theta\}$, $[\mathcal{L}_u], [\mathcal{L}_\phi], [\mathcal{L}_\theta]$ are linear operators [11,12], $\{\delta^u\}^T = [u_1, u_2, u_3]$, $\{\delta^\phi\} = \{\phi\}$, $\{\delta^\theta\} = \{\theta\}$, $\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{22}, \dots, \epsilon_{31}$ are the strain components, E_1, E_2, E_3 are the electric field components and g_1, g_2, g_3 are the thermal gradients in the three directions.

Constitutive Relations

The equations for quasistatic thermopiezoelectricity are:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\sigma\} &= [C] [\{\epsilon\} - \{\epsilon^0\}] - [e] \{E\} - \{\gamma\} \theta \\ \{D\} &= [e]^T [\{\epsilon\} - \{\epsilon^0\}] + [\epsilon] \{E\} + \{p\} \theta \\ \eta &= \gamma^T [\{\epsilon\} - \{\epsilon^0\}] + [p] \{E\} + \alpha_v \theta \\ \{h\} &= [k] \nabla \theta \\ \{E\} &= -\nabla \phi \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\{\sigma\}$ is the stress vector, $\{D\}$ is the electric displacement field, η the entropy per unit volume, $\{\epsilon\}$ is the strain vector, $\{\epsilon^0\}$ is the initial strain vector, $\{E\}$ is the electric field vector, $[C]$ the elasticity matrix, $[e]$ the permittivity matrix, $[k]$ the conductivity matrix, $[e]$ is the piezoelectric matrix, $\{\gamma\}$ is the vector of thermal expansion coefficients, $\{p\}$ is the vector of pyroelectric constants, $\{h\}$ the vector of heat flux, ∇ is the gradient operator, $\alpha_v = \rho C_v \theta_o^{-1}$, ρ is the density, C_v is the specific heat at constant volume, θ_o is the reference temperature, θ the temperature rise from reference temperature and ϕ is the electric potential (voltage).

Equations of Motion

The finite element equations are obtained by variational principles. Three energy functionals corresponding to the mechanical displacement, electric and temperature fields are first derived and variations with respect to the independent displacement, electric and temperature variables are then taken to obtain the global system equations as [5,6,11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} M_{uu} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{U} \\ \ddot{\phi} \\ \ddot{\theta} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C_{uu} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \theta_0 K_{\theta u} & -\theta_0 K_{\theta \phi} & H_{\theta \theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{U} \\ \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_{uu} & K_{u\phi} & -K_{u\theta} \\ K_{\phi u} & -K_{\phi\phi} & K_{\phi\theta} \\ 0 & 0 & K_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U \\ \phi \\ \theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_u \\ F_\phi \\ F_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where M_{uu} is the mass matrix, $K_{uu}, K_{\phi\phi}, K_{\theta\theta}$ are the mechanical, electrical and thermal stiffness

matrices, $K_{u\phi}$, $K_{u\theta}$, $K_{\phi\theta}$ are the coupling matrices, $H_{\theta\theta}$ the thermal rate stiffness matrix, C_{uu} is the damping matrix, and F_u , F_ϕ , F_θ are the mechanical, electrical and thermal load vectors, respectively. The detailed expressions for the element matrices are available in [11]. The matrix coefficients are obtained by Gaussian integration in each material layer [11].

Solution of Finite Element Equations of Motion

In the finite element solution procedure, the thermal, electrical and mechanical displacements are calculated separately to improve the computational efficiency. The thermal field is first obtained by solving the third of Equations (3) using a forward difference time integration scheme. Then the displacement and electrical potential equations are decoupled using Guyan condensation to obtain a reduced system of equations

$$M_{uu} \ddot{U} + D_{uu} \dot{U} + K^* U = F_u + K_{u\phi} K_{\phi\phi}^{-1} F_\phi + (K_{u\theta} - K_{u\phi} K_{\phi\phi}^{-1} K_{\phi\theta}) \theta \quad (4)$$

from which the displacement field U is obtained using the Newmark time integration scheme, where

$$K^* + K_{uu} + K_{u\phi} K_{\phi\phi}^{-1} K_{\phi u} \quad (5)$$

The electrical potential is then obtained from the second of Equations (3) as

$$\phi = K_{\phi\phi}^{-1} (K_{\phi u} U + K_{\phi\theta} \theta - F_\phi) \quad (6)$$

A distinction is made between the electric potential at the sensors and that at the actuators. The electric potential at the sensors is amplified and fed back to the actuators to control the structure as described below.

Control Algorithms

For control problems, the electrical force F_ϕ , assumed to be applied at the actuators, is taken as the control as feedback force F_f given by

$$F_f = [K_{u\phi}^A] [K_{\phi\phi}^A]^{-1} F_\phi \quad (7)$$

and the control law is implemented on the electrical charges as

$$F_\phi = -G \phi^s \quad (8)$$

where the superscripts A and S denote actuators and sensor quantities, respectively, and G is a gain matrix. The control problem effectively reduces to determining the gain matrix and substituting equations (7) and (8) into equation (4) to obtain the closed-loop responses. Among the numerous methods available for calculating gain matrix [2], the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) is used in this study because of its wide use. However, options for the use simple control algorithms such as the independent modal space control (IMSC) and the modified independent modal space control (MIMSC) are provided to facilitate optimization studies. In general, these control laws provide various means of minimizing the performance index

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty [Z^T Q Z + F_f^T R F_f] dt \quad (9)$$

subject to

$$\dot{Z}(t) = A Z(t) + B F_f \quad (10)$$

where $\{Z(t)\}^T = [U(t) \dot{U}(t)]$ and A and B are the system matrices, Q and R are weighting factors

which are related to the control effectiveness and control energy consumption, respectively [2,11].

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Several numerical example problems have been used to verify various aspects of the theoretical formulations, as detailed in Reference [11]. The results obtained generally compared well with other published results [11]. In this paper, simple examples on how the computational tool SMARTCOM can be used for the design of actively controlled structure are presented. The problem configuration is shown in Figure 1. Two layers of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) films are bonded to the top and bottom of an aluminum beam. The PVDF films are 0.001m thick and the aluminium beam is 0.005 m thick and 0.005m wide. Two lengths of the beam, 0.6m and 0.06m, respectively, were considered to study the influence of beam flexibility. The material properties are shown in Table 1. The beam is subjected to a point step load of 0.1N at the free end. The hybrid structure is modelled by a total of nine elements - three for each of the PVDF layers and three for the aluminium beam.

A natural frequency analysis is first carried out and the first 10 natural frequencies for the two beam length cases are shown in Table 2. The effects of the piezoelectric material layers are accounted for in the natural frequency calculations. As shown in the table, the frequencies of the beam with $l=0.06\text{m}$ are much higher than those for the beam with $l=0.6\text{m}$, since the former is much stiffer. Based on the frequencies, time steps equal to or less than 0.005 sec and 0.00005 sec were used for beams with $l=0.6\text{m}$ and $l=0.06\text{m}$, respectively, for the transient analysis. The transient displacement and voltage solutions for the two beam cases are obtained using the modal superposition method. The gain matrix and for the closed loop solution is obtained by the IMSC method.

For the case of the beam with length of 0.6 m , the modal weighting factor R_i was selected as 10 for each of the 10 modes used in the analysis. The open and closed loop displacement solutions are shown in Figure 2 and the corresponding voltages are shown in Figure 3. Control was achieved in about 0.12 seconds. For the case of the beam with length of 0.06 m the weighting factor R_i was also set to 10 for each mode and the open and closed loop displacement solutions are shown in Figure 4. As shown in the figure, control could not be obtained after 3 milliseconds. In fact, the trend of the closed loop solution indicates that it would take a very long time for the solution to stabilize at the mean displacement or voltage. This shows that the value of $R_i = 10$ was not efficient for this structure. Consequently, the value of the weighting factor R_i was changed to $R_i=100$ for each mode. This corresponds to increasing the effort or energy to control the structure. The new displacement and voltage solutions are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. Now control is achieved in about 1.5 milliseconds.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented an integrated finite element control capability for design/analysis of smart composite structures. The structure, sensors, and actuators are modelled by 20-node thermopiezoelectric elements and control is achieved by the IMSC and LQR algorithms. A computational software called SMARTCOM has been developed based on the method. Numerical example problems have been used to verify the software tool and the results obtained show that SMARTCOM can be and effectively used to model actively controlled structures.

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Table 1. Material Properties for Sensory/Active Beams

Property	PVDF	Aluminium
Elastic Properties		
E ₁₁ (GPa)	2.0	68.9
E ₂₂ (GPa)	2.0	68.9
E ₃₃ (GPa)	2.0	68.9
G ₂₃ (GPa)	0.775	27.6
G ₁₃ (GPa)	0.775	27.6
G ₁₂ (GPa)	0.775	27.6
v ₁₂	0.29	0.25
v ₁₃	0.29	0.25
v ₂₃	0.29	0.25
Piezoelectric Stress Constants (C/m ²)		
e ₃₁	0.046	
e ₃₂	0.046	
Electric Permittivity (10 ⁻¹² F/m)		
ε ₁₁	106.2	0
ε ₂₂	106.2	0
ε ₃₃	106.2	0
Mass Density ρ(kg/m ³)	1800	2769

Table 2 Natural Frequencies of Beams with PVDF Layers

Mode No.	Frequencies (Hz)	
	Case 1: ℓ = 0.6m	Case 2: ℓ=0.06m
1	12.51	1249.0
2	12.52	1249.1
3	79.75	7717.4
4	79.76	7717.6
5	239.94	13605.0
6	239.96	22031.0
7	628.02	22196.0
8	628.44	22369.0
9	1360.5	41117.0
10	1879.9	51530.0

Figure 1: Schematics of Beam with Piezoelectric Sensor and Actuator

Figure 2: Open and Closed Loop Displacement at Free End of Beam ($\ell = 0.6\text{ m}$)

Figure 3: Open and Closed Loop Voltages at Fixed End of Beam ($\ell = 0.6 \text{ m}$)

Figure 4: Open and Closed Loop Displacements at Free End of Beam ($\ell = 0.06 \text{ m}$, $R_i = 10$)

Figure 5: Open and Closed Loop Displacements at Free End of Beam ($\ell=0.06$ m, $R_i = 100$)

Figure 6: Open and Closed Loop Voltages at Fixed End of Beam ($\ell=0.06$ m, $R_i = 100$)